

The Q(5) Raman Line of Carbon Monoxide and its q-Gaussian Function

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna

Department of Applied Science and Technology, Polytechnic University of Turin, Italy

Email: amelia.sparavigna@polito.it

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Abstract – In an article by Thibault et al., 2002, we can find measurements of Raman linewidths in the Q branch of the carbon monoxide in the case of mixtures with Argon at different temperatures. A plot is available for the Q(5) line and its fitted Voigt function. Here we show that a q-Gaussian Tsallis function can be used for fitting too. The fitted q-Gaussian has the wings which are not Lorentzian. The difference between the experimental data and the fitted q-Gaussian seems being lower than that obtained in the case of using the Voigt function. A discussion about the time correlation functions related to some line shapes is also proposed.

Keywords: Raman spectroscopy, q-Gaussian Tsallis lines, Time correlation functions, WolframAlpha by Wolfram Research

Introduction

The Voigt functions, convolutions of Gaussian and Lorentzian functions, and the q-Gaussian functions can be used as line shapes in Raman spectroscopy for the analysis of spectra (Sparavigna, 2023). The Voigtian convolution possesses a bell shape with a Gaussian kernel and wings (tails) which are of the Lorentzian form. According to Cope and Lovett, 1987, the asymptotic solution of Voigtian expansion has the leading term equal to $a_0 / \pi x^2$. The Voigt functions, or their approximations as pseudo-Voigtian functions, which are linear combinations of Gaussian and Lorentzian functions, are suggested for instance in Meier, 2005, because of their corresponding correlation functions related to the fundamental mechanisms of Raman photonic emissions. Moreover, the Voigt profiles are intermediate between the Lorentzian and Gaussian outlines. The reason of using the Voigt functions is therefore also motivated by the fact that “intermediate” profiles are usually displayed by the Raman spectral lines (Kirillov, 2004).

The q-Gaussian functions have intermediate profiles too. The q-Gaussians, also known as "Tsallis functions", are probability distributions derived from the Tsallis statistics (Tsallis, 1988, 1995, Hanel et al., 2009). The q-Gaussians are based on a generalized form of the exponential function (see discussion in Sparavigna, 2022), characterized by a continuous parameter q in the range $1 < q < 3$. As given by Umarov et al., 2008, the q-Gaussian is based on function $f(x) = C e_q(-\beta x^2)$, where $e_q(\cdot)$ is the q-exponential function and C a constant. The q-exponential has expression: $exp_q(u) = [1 + (1 - q)u]^{1/(1-q)}$. The function $f(x)$ possesses a bell-shaped profile, and in the case that we have the peak at position x_o , the q-Gaussian is:

$$q\text{-Gaussian} = C exp_q(-\beta(x - x_o)^2) = C[1 - (1 - q)\beta(x - x_o)^2]^{1/(1-q)} \quad (1)$$

For q equal to 2, the q-Gaussian is the Cauchy-Lorentzian distribution (Naudts, 2009). For q close to 1, the q-Gaussian is a Gaussian. Consequently, for the q -parameter between 1 and 2, the shape of the q-Gaussian function is intermediate between the Gaussian and the Lorentzian profiles.

The q-Gaussian functions can mimic the Voigt convolutions, but they are different functions, in particular for what is regarding the behavior of the wings. So let us stress once more that the Voigt function, as told by Townsend, 2008, “looks like Gaussian for small x (i.e., near line center), and like Lorentzian for large x (i.e., out in line wings)”. We can also appreciate the same by observing the pseudo-Voigt function, which is generally used for approximating the Voigt function. Being the pseudo-Voigt the linear combination of Gaussian and Lorentzian functions, the wings must be necessarily Lorentzian and the kernel Gaussian-like. Consequently, if we use Voigt functions or pseudo-Voigt functions for fitting spectra, the wings of the Raman lines will be always described by a Lorentzian behavior. However, is this always the experimental case? That is, are we always observing Lorentzian wings for the Raman bands? To answer these questions, we started investigation in [ChemRxiv1](#). We observed that a generalization of the pseudo-Voigt functions obtained by means of a linear combination of two q-Gaussians can help us in describing the leading term of the line wings. In this manner, we can quantitatively “measure” the wing power law as well as answering qualitatively whether it is Lorentzian or not. The q-Gaussians are therefore the proper solution for investigation. Actually, for the spectra previously considered (Sparavigna, 2023), the fitted functions are successfully in several cases, for instance graphite, [ChemRxiv2](#), anatase [ChemRxiv3](#), SERS spectra, [ChemRxiv4](#), and so on, [SSRN](#).

For what is regarding the physics of Voigt function, let us remember the convolution theorem. This theorem states that the Fourier transform of a convolution is the product of the Fourier transforms of the convoluted functions. It means that the two related phenomena must have probability distributions which are independent (see discussion in Sparavigna, 2023). In the case of the Voigt convolution, the two distributions are those that we can find discussed for photonic emission in Svelto, 1970. They are the exponential and the Gaussian distribution, so that a spectral Lorentzian function is generally assumed as describing the photonic emission of the material (or the broadening due to photonic interactions with phonons), and the Gaussian function as representing the thermal effect (or the effect of instrumentation). In the case of the q-Gaussian function, the physics of the q-parameter is in its ability to evaluate the power law of the wings, as previously discussed. Here we start considering further lines from Raman spectroscopy, such as those of the isolated lines of gases, to investigate the behavior of the wings by means of a q-Gaussian power law.

Convolution

As previously told, the Voigt profile is a convolution of a Lorentz distribution L and a Gaussian distribution G given by:

$$V(k; \sigma, \gamma) = \{G * L\}(k) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} G(k'; \sigma) L(k - k'; \gamma) dk'$$

where k , in spectroscopy, is representing the shift from the line center k_0 , and

$$G(k; \sigma) = \frac{e^{-k^2/(2\sigma^2)}}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}}, L(k; \gamma) = \frac{\gamma}{\pi(k^2 + \gamma^2)}.$$

The convolution theorem states that the Fourier transform of a convolution of two functions is the pointwise product of their Fourier transforms. Let us consider two functions $g(x), h(x)$ and their Fourier transforms $G(k), H(k)$. The convolution is:

$$r(x) = \{g * h\}(x) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(\xi) h(x - \xi) d\xi$$

And according to the convolution theorem¹:

¹ <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/ConvolutionTheorem.html>

$$F\{r(x)\}(k) = F\{g*h\}(k) = F\{g(x)\}(k) \cdot F\{h(x)\}(k) = G(k) \cdot H(k),$$

Operator F indicates the Fourier transform.

Burke et al., 2019, in their introduction to radio astronomy, consider the convolution theorem “easily proven” and with “many practical applications”. The authors of the book are also telling that when a signal g is the input of an amplifier, which possesses a specific response function h , the function H given above is known as the transfer function of the instrumentation (Burke et al., 2019).

From the theorem we have also:

$$R(k) = \{G*H\}(k) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} G(\xi)H(k - \xi)d\xi$$

$$F\{R(k)\}(x) = F\{\{G*H\}(k)\}(x) = F\{G(k)\}(x) \cdot F\{H(k)\}(x)$$

$$F\{R(k)\}(x) = g(x) \cdot h(x).$$

Consequently, the Fourier transform of the Voigt function is the pointwise product of the Fourier transforms of Gaussian and Lorentzian functions:

$$F\{G*L\}(x) = F\{G(k)\}(x) \cdot F\{L(k)\}(x) = g(x) \cdot l(x)$$

The Fourier transform of a Gaussian is a Gaussian, so that, in the Wolfram formalism²:

$$g(x) = F\{e^{-ak^2}\}(x) = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{a}}e^{-\pi^2x^2/a},$$

and in the case of the Lorentzian function³:

$$l(x) = F\left\{\frac{1}{\pi} \frac{\frac{1}{2}\Gamma}{(k-k_0)^2 + (\Gamma/2)^2}\right\}(x) = e^{-2\pi i x k_0 - \Gamma \pi |x|}.$$

This is the characteristic function of the Cauchy distribution. If we consider the center at zero:

$$l(x) = F\left\{\frac{\Gamma}{2\pi} \frac{1}{k^2 + (\Gamma/2)^2}\right\}(x) = e^{-\Gamma \pi |x|}$$

Let us note that methods for the fast computation of Voigt Function are based on the Fourier transform too (Schreier, 1992, Mendenhall, 2007, see please also the discussion by Vogman, 2010). The use of the convolution theorem has been also appreciated for the comparison of different algorithms for evaluating the Voigt function (Abousahl et al., 1997). The approach by Abousahl and coworkers is based on F^{-1} Fourier anti-transform, so that:

$$V(k) = \{G*L\}(k) = F^{-1}\{g(x) \cdot l(x)\}(k)$$

Before considering the time correlation function corresponding to a q-Gaussian, let us further discuss for a while convolution and transfer function.

As already made in [ChemRxiv5](#), let us consider the words by Orazio Svelto, 1970, about the homogeneous broadening of the photonic emission. In the case that we have a dipole damped oscillator model, we can observe the spectral line of the spontaneous emission with a “natural” or “intrinsic” broadening. This homogeneous broadening produces a line profile described by a Lorentzian function. Svelto is also mentioning the photon-phonon interaction as generating homogeneous broadening and therefore a Lorentzian line shape too. An inhomogeneous broadening (such as those caused by the Doppler effect and thermal effect) is giving a Gaussian line shape. However, in spectroscopy, the most

²<https://mathworld.wolfram.com/FourierTransformGaussian.html>

³<https://mathworld.wolfram.com/FourierTransformLorentzianFunction.html>

observed case is that of an intermediate profile, given by the convolution of the resonance relative probability and the broadening function, because natural band can be modified by different mechanisms (Svelto, 1970).

We have mentioned the natural broadening giving a Lorentzian profile, the thermal broadening introducing a Gaussian profile, and the general intermediate profiles as the most common cases. A consequence is that the Voigt profile, that is the convolution of Gaussian and Lorentzian functions, is generally used to simulate the intermediate case. Voigt profile is also used in the case of the spin resonance lines. In solids, these lines “are broadened by a number of mechanisms” (Stoneham, 1972). “Some of these mechanisms give a Gaussian lineshape, such as dipolar broadening in concentrated crystals (Van Vleck 1948) and strain broadening by dislocations (Stoneham 1966, 1969). Other mechanisms lead to a Lorentzian lineshape, such as the relaxation broadening due to the finite lifetime of a state” (Stoneham, 1972, is referring to the analogous broadening mechanism that we find in Svelto, 1970). According to Stoneham, “If the mechanisms which lead to Lorentzian and Gaussian broadening are *independent*, the lineshape is just the convolution of a Gaussian and a Lorentzian”.

“Alternatively, [we can] suppose that the line is scanned by a spectrophotometer with a Gaussian sensitivity function” (Tatum, 2022). Then, in this experimental framework, we have the convolution of the line with the instrumental function profile. Let us remember that “the general expression that takes account of all the instrumentally induced distortion of the true band shape can be called the instrument function” (Seshadri and Jones, 1963). It is also known as the “instrumental transfer function” (Merlen et al., 2017). As told by S.G. Rautian, 1958: “Each monochromatic component $\varphi(x)dx$ of the true radiation is replaced by the apparatus [instrument] function, as a result of which, at some arbitrary point x' , there is created an illumination (or current) $a(x' - x)\varphi(x)dx$. Other monochromatic components of the true distribution also make a corresponding contribution to the illumination at the point x' , and as a result the observed distribution $f(x')$ will be expressed by the following integral”:

$$f(x') = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} a(x' - x)\varphi(x)dx.$$

In the integral we have function $a(x)$ that considers “distortions both in the optical and recording parts of the apparatus” (Rautian, 1958). In Rautian, 1958, we can find several different instrumental functions that can be convoluted with the true radiation. And the true radiation can be a convolution of different broadening mechanisms. The Voigt convolution is based on Lorentzian and Gaussian profiles because the analysis starts from a Lorentzian damping model (natural radiation) with a weight which is a Gaussian one. Different approaches exist (Kirillov, 2004), so that the true radiation line can be assumed different from a Lorentzian function; moreover, the weight function can be different from a pure Gaussian function.

In Merlen et al., 2017, researchers are telling that “If we do not take into account the instrumental transfer function that can be negligible in many cases (...), the total intensity of one phonon mode with a wavevector q_0 and a frequency $\omega(q_0)$, in a perfect crystal, is spread on a symmetric profile which is Lorentzian”. Merlen et al. are also discussing the presence of asymmetric peaks in the framework of the approach by Richter et al., 1981. In the case of investigating the first order region of the Raman spectra of carbonaceous materials, for its fitting procedure, Merlen et al. suggest the use of Lorentzian and Gaussian functions for symmetric profiles and of the Breit-Wigner-Fano (BWF) line shape for asymmetric peaks (in particular they tell for the case of “One band: The G band is fitted by a Lorentzian if symmetric, and by a BWF if not symmetric”). We have discussed the G and G' bands of graphite in [ChemRxiv2](#) and we used q-Gaussians. We used q-Gaussians too for other carbonaceous materials (biochar and nanotubes) in [SSRN](#). The behavior of the peaks we considered is q-Gaussian, that is, not Lorentzian or Gaussian but q-Gaussian. For what is regarding the BWF asymmetric line shape, we started investigation about the [Raman LO mode band](#) in Silicon Carbide.

“The physical argument employed in establishing the Voigt profile is that the effects of Doppler & collision broadening are decoupled. Thus we argue that every point on a collision-broadened lineshape is further broadened by Doppler effects” (Ronald K. Hanson, 2018). Hanson is mentioning refinements with Galatry profiles (collision narrowing) and Berman profiles (speed-dependent broadening).

WolframAlpha approach

Let us consider software WolframAlpha to investigate the behavior of Voigt time correlation function. Software is providing the plot of the function and its Fourier transform, as in the following example.

$$\mathcal{F}_t \left[\exp(-|t|) \exp\left(-\frac{t^2}{2}\right) \right] (\omega) = \frac{1}{2} e^{-1/2(\omega+i)^2} \left(-\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{1-i\omega}{\sqrt{2}}\right) + e^{2i\omega} \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{1+i\omega}{\sqrt{2}}\right) + 1 \right)$$

We can also find some different forms of the Fourier transform:

Alternate forms

$$\frac{1}{2} e^{-1/2(\omega+i)^2} \left(\operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{1-i\omega}{\sqrt{2}}\right) + e^{2i\omega} \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{1+i\omega}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \right)$$

$$-\frac{1}{2} e^{-1/2(\omega+i)^2} \left(\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{1-i\omega}{\sqrt{2}}\right) - e^{2i\omega} \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{1+i\omega}{\sqrt{2}}\right) - 1 \right)$$

$$\frac{1}{2} e^{-1/2(\omega+i)^2} \left(-\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{1-i\omega}{\sqrt{2}}\right) + e^{2i\omega} \left(1 - \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{1+i\omega}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \right) + 1 \right)$$

Let us also consider the Laplace Transform of the Voigt time correlation function.

Input interpretation	Result
$\mathcal{L}_t \left[e^{-\sqrt{t^2}} e^{-t^2/2} \right] (s)$	$\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} e^{1/2(s+1)^2} \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{s+1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$

where erfc is the complementary error function. Function erf is the error function.

We can obtain the Fourier Transform passing from s to $i w$.

Regarding the behavior of the series expansion:

Series expansion at $w=\infty$

$$\left(-\frac{i}{w} + \left(\frac{1}{w}\right)^2 + O\left(\left(\frac{1}{w}\right)^4\right)\right) - \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} e^{-w^2/2+iw+1/2} i^{2[\arg(2iw+1)/(2\pi)]} + \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} e^{-w^2/2+iw+1/2}$$

q-Gaussians and Bessel functions

For what is regarding the q-Gaussian function and its Fourier transform, we need to tell that the specific formulation of the transform is quite complex (Rodrigues & Giraldi, 2015). However, we can find that the Fourier transform of the q-Gaussian contains the K functions (modified Bessel function of the second kind). Here, let us consider (1) in the following form, with dimensionless variable w about $w_0 = 0$:

$$q\text{-Gaussian} = C \exp_q(-w^2) = C[1 - (1 - q)w^2]^{1/(1-q)} \quad (2)$$

and search for the Fourier transform of it, remembering that the Fourier transform of a Lorentzian line shape is producing a time correlation function which is an exponential decaying with time, and that, in the case of the Gaussian line shape, we have a correlation with is a Gaussian function of time. Being the q-Gaussian a line shape which is intermediate between Lorentzian and Gaussian profiles, the related time correlation function must be intermediate between exponential and Gaussian functions.

As previously told, Rodrigues and Giraldi, 2015, have considered in detail the Fourier transform of the q-Gaussian functions. Here we use a more phenomenological approach. Let us start from the link between the q-Gaussians and the Bessel functions.

In [Wikipedia](#) we find that the “Bessel functions can be described as Fourier transforms of powers of quadratic functions”. Function K_ν is a modified Bessel function of the second kind, order ν . For instance:

$$2 K_0(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{e^{i\omega t}}{\sqrt{t^2 + 1}} dt.$$

To have further cases, we can use the on-line Fourier transform calculator, at <https://www.wolframalpha.com>. Following the notation in Wikipedia, we can find, for instance:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 + (At)^2)^{-1/2} e^{i\omega t} dt = \frac{1}{\sqrt{A^2}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \cdot K_0\left(\frac{|\omega|}{\sqrt{A^2}}\right)$$

Note that, in this example, we can see evidenced the time/frequency scaling.

The Fourier transform (WolframAlpha) of the function with exponent $-1/(q-1)$, that is $1/(1-q)$ as in (2), from the frequency domain w to the time domain t (dimensionless variables) is:

$$F_w[(1 + w^2)^{-1/(q-1)}](t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)} \cdot 2^{\frac{q-2}{q-1}} \cdot |t|^{\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{1}{2}} \cdot K_{\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{1}{2}}(t \operatorname{sgn}(t))$$

Posing $\xi = 1/(q-1)$: $F_w[(1 + w^2)^{-\xi}](t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\xi)} \cdot 2^{(q-2)\xi} \cdot |t|^{\xi - \frac{1}{2}} \cdot K_{\xi - \frac{1}{2}}(t \operatorname{sgn}(t))$

To illustrate the behavior of the Fourier transform, let us consider different values of q , starting from $q=3$, including $q=2$ (Lorentzian), to find the corresponding time correlations (see [Zenodo](#) for discussion about time correlation in Raman spectroscopy).

From WolframAlpha, we have:

$$F_w[(1 + w^2)^{-1/(3-1)}](t) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} K_0(t \operatorname{sgn}(t))$$

By the way, the q-Gaussian is defined for q ranging from 1 to 3.

Fourier transform in the case $q=3$ (plot courtesy WolframAlpha)

$$F_w[(1 + w^2)^{-1/(2.5-1)}](t) = 0.930437 \cdot |t|^{0.166667} \cdot K_{0.166667}(t \operatorname{sgn}(t))$$

$$F_w[(1 + w^2)^{-1/(2-1)}](t) = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} e^{-|t|} \quad (a)$$

(Fourier transform of the Lorentzian function). In (a) we can find the Laplace distribution.

$$F_w[(1 + w^2)^{-1/(1.9999-1)}](t) = 0.999988 \cdot |t|^{0.5001} \cdot K_{0.5001}(t \operatorname{sgn}(t)) \quad (a')$$

We can deduce that the exponential is equal to a K Bessel function multiplied by a square root, so that:

$$K_{0.5}(t \operatorname{sgn} t) = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{|t|}} e^{-|t|}.$$

$$F_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.9-1)}](t) = 0.977728 \cdot |t|^{0.611111} \cdot K_{0.611111}(t \operatorname{sgn} t) \quad (b)$$

$$F_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.7-1)}](t) = 0.838525 \cdot |t|^{0.928571} \cdot K_{0.928571}(t \operatorname{sgn} t) \quad (c)$$

$$F_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.5-1)}](t) = \frac{0.626657}{t^2} \cdot e^{-|t|} \cdot |t|^2 \cdot (|t|+1) = 0.626657 \cdot e^{-|t|} \cdot (|t|+1) \quad (d)$$

$$F_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.4999-1)}](t) = 0.499777 \cdot |t|^{1.5} \cdot K_{1.5}(t \operatorname{sgn} t)$$

We have, as given by WolframAlpha, that: $K_{1.5}(t) = \frac{1.253314137}{\sqrt{t}} \cdot e^{-t} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{t} + 1\right)$, and therefore (d).

$$F_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.4-1)}](t) = 0.265962 \cdot |t|^2 \cdot K_2(t \operatorname{sgn} t)$$

$$F_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.3-1)}](t) = 0.0714233 \cdot |t|^{2.83333} \cdot K_{2.83333}(t \operatorname{sgn} t)$$

$$F_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.15-1)}](t) = 0.000050 \cdot |t|^{6.16667} \cdot K_{6.16667}(t \operatorname{sgn} t)$$

Fourier transforms of four cases given above (plots courtesy WolframAlpha).

Let us add some further screenshots (WolframAlpha source).

$$\mathcal{F}_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.25-1)}](t) = \frac{1}{t^4 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^4} |t|^{3.5} e^{-t \operatorname{sgn}(t)} \sqrt{t \operatorname{sgn}(t)} (0.0261107 t^3 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^3 + 0.156664 t^2 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^2 + 0.391661 t \operatorname{sgn}(t) + 0.391661)$$

$$\mathcal{F}_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.2-1)}](t) = \frac{1}{t^5 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^5} |t|^{4.5} e^{-t \operatorname{sgn}(t)} \sqrt{t \operatorname{sgn}(t)} (0.00326384 t^4 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^4 + 0.0326384 t^3 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^3 + 0.146873 t^2 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^2 + 0.342703 t \operatorname{sgn}(t) + 0.342703)$$

$$\mathcal{F}_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.125-1)}](t) = \frac{1}{t^8 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^8} |t|^{7.5} e^{-t \operatorname{sgn}(t)} \sqrt{t \operatorname{sgn}(t)} (1.94276 \times 10^{-6} t^7 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^7 + 0.0000543973 t^6 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^6 + 0.000734364 t^5 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^5 + 0.0061197 t^4 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^4 + 0.0336583 t^3 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^3 + 0.12117 t^2 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^2 + 0.262535 t \operatorname{sgn}(t) + 0.262535)$$

Using the results given above and considering the scaling $(q - 1)w^2$ into $t/\sqrt{(q - 1)}$, we can plot some time correlations as in the Figure 1a,b (linear and semi logarithmic scales).

Figure 1a: Fourier transforms of some q -Gaussians as given by WolframAlpha, for some values of the q parameter.

Figure 1b: The same as in the Figure 3, in semi-logarithmic scale. For $q=2$, we have a correlation which is an exponential function (straight red line). For q closer to 1, the curve is Gaussian-like (parabolic behavior in the semi-log plot).

In Wikipedia, https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Distribuzione_di_Laplace, we can find mentioned the Sargan distributions, given in the following form:

$$f_p(x) = \frac{1}{2} \exp(-\alpha|x|) \frac{1 + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j \alpha^j |x|^j}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^p j! \beta_j}.$$

In the screenshots and in (d), we can find suggested the Sargan distributions indeed. As told by Kotz and coworkers (2001), "For $\lambda = r + 1/2$, where r is a non-negative integer, the Bessel function K_λ has the closed form":

$$K_{r+1/2}(u) = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2u}} e^{-u} \sum_{k=0}^r \frac{(r+k)!}{(r-k)!k!} (2u)^{-k} \quad (*)$$

This is formula A.0.10 in Kotz et al., 2001. For $r = 0$, we have (A.0.11):

$$K_{1/2}(u) = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2u}} e^{-u}.$$

(see also the discussion at 4.4.3 in Kotz et al., 2001).

Let us consider again $K_{1.5}(t) = \frac{1.253314137}{\sqrt{t}} \cdot e^{(-t)} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{t} + 1\right)$, for instance. It is easy to find that this expression agrees with (*). For a further discussion, see Appendix.

We have not to be surprised to find time correlations containing Bessel functions. For instance, in Hall and Helfand, 1982, we can find them in time-correlation functions of the conformational state relaxation in polymers. Hall and Helfand studied the “relaxation processes in polymer molecules which proceed via conformational transitions of the chain backbone from one rotational isomeric state to another. ... The resulting correlation functions contain a modified Bessel function which is associated with the diffusional nature of the process. This functional form has recently proven useful in fitting time-correlation functions determined in polymer simulations, which indicates that it will be of value in fitting data obtained in relaxation experiments on polymers” (Hall & Helfand, 1982).

Regarding the Laplace transform of the q-Gaussian, here a Wolfram Alpha result.

Input interpretation

$\mathcal{L}_w[(w^2 + 1)^{-1/(q-1)}](s)$

$\mathcal{L}_t[f(t)](s)$ is the Laplace transform of $f(t)$ with complex argument s

Result

$$\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)} s^{-(q-3)/(2(q-1))} \left(-\sqrt{\pi} 2^{1/(1-q)+1} \Gamma\left(2 + \frac{1}{1-q}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{2-q}{q-1}\right) \mathbf{H}_{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{1-q}}(s) + \right.$$

$$\left. \sqrt{\pi} 2^{1/(1-q)+1} \Gamma\left(\frac{3}{2} + \frac{1}{1-q}\right) \Gamma\left(-\frac{q-3}{2(q-1)}\right) J_{\frac{q-3}{2(q-1)}}(s) + \right.$$

$$\left. 2^{q/(q-1)} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{q-3}{q-1}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{q+1}{2(q-1)}\right) J_{-\frac{q-3}{2(q-1)}}(s) \right)$$

$\Gamma(x)$ is the gamma function
 $J_n(z)$ is the Bessel function of the first kind
 $\mathbf{H}_n(x)$ is the Struve function

Egelstaff-Schofield lineshape

With the aim of formulating the Fourier transform of the q-Gaussian function in a simpler manner (that is, to have a simpler function for the time correlation), in a previous article we discussed the Egelstaff-Schofield (ES) line shapes and the related fitted q-Gaussians. Let us stress that the ES profiles can be Fourier transformed into a simple analytical expression (Kirillov, 1999); moreover, the ES profiles can be mimicked quite well by the q-Gaussians. Therefore, the Fourier transform of the q-Gaussian function could be approximated by the following formula:

$$\Phi(t) = \exp\left\{-\left[(t^2 + \tau_1^2)^{1/2} - \tau_1\right]/\tau_2\right\}.$$

According to Kirillov, 1999, we have this function which becomes Gaussian for $t \ll \tau_1$, and an exponential for $t \gg \tau_1$. In a [previous discussion](#), we used for the correlation the stretched exponential too. Further work is required to establish what can be a better approximation for the time correlation of the q-Gaussian line shape.

Let us write the previous expression as:

$$\Phi(t) = \exp\{ -[(t^2 + a^2)^{1/2} - a]/b \}.$$

The following plot is giving the behavior of the function.

Fig.2: Behavior of the Egelstaff-Schofield time correlation. From the semi log scale, we can appreciate the deviation from the exponential decay at short times.

Breit-Wigner-Fano lineshape

Since we have mentioned it before, let us consider how can we express the time correlation function related to the Breit-Wigner-Fano line shape.

Let us consider it as defined in Origin: <https://www.originlab.com/doc/Origin-Help/BWF-PAFunc> , with the same parameters. In WolframAlpha, input $(1+w/40)^2/(1+(w/4)^2)$, we have plots:

Plots courtesy WolframAlpha for the input given above.

The Fourier transform (Wolfram Alpha) is given as:

$$\mathcal{F}_w\left[\frac{\left(1 + \frac{w}{40}\right)^2}{1 + \left(\frac{w}{4}\right)^2}\right](t) = \frac{1}{50} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \delta(t) + \frac{1}{25} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} e^{-4t} ((99 - 20i) e^{8t} \theta(-t) + (99 + 20i) \theta(t))$$

Plot of the BWF Fourier transform (courtesy WolframAlpha).

In the case that $t > 0$, the Forier transform reduces to: $(99/25 + 4i/5) \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} e^{-4t}$.

In general, for input $(q+w)^2/(1+w^2)$, that is $\frac{(q+w)^2}{(1+w^2)}$ as in Misochko and Lebedev, 2015, we find (WolframAlpha):

$$\sqrt{2\pi} \delta(t) + \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} (q^2 - 1) e^{-t} (e^{2t} \theta(-t) + \theta(t)) - i \sqrt{2\pi} q e^{-t} (e^{2t} \theta(-t) - \theta(t))$$

This is the expression given for q and t real. In the case $t > 0$, it remains the decaying exponential.

Beyond the Voigt profile

Besides the behavior of the wings, a relevant problem for the use of Voigt functions needs to be noted. To evaluate these functions, it is required a numerical approach because the convolution is an integral which cannot be solved analytically. The result is consequently depending on the model representing the convolution and, also, on the language used to implement the calculus and the related compiler required to obtain the numerical results. In the case that we have the experimental data at our disposal, a question could be: can we reproduce the results obtained by means of the Voigt function if we do not know the used models and compilers? Some could claim that, today, due to the speed of computers we have no problems in any numerical calculus, however the problem of reproducibility remains because it has nothing to do with the speed of the calculus.

Forthomme et al., 2015, asserted that the “Voigt profile (VP) is the standard lineshape model used in high resolution spectroscopy databases for its simplicity and its fast computation time. However, with the ever-increasing sensitivity and accuracy of measurement techniques, more subtle effects on the experimental data are now commonly observed”. It is told, by Forthomme and coworkers, that the Voigt profile needs to be revised. At low to moderate pressures, the “attempts to model measured lineshapes with a VP typically leaves a ”w” shaped residual”. This difference is “associated with the narrowing that is not represented in the VP” (Forthomme et al. are mentioning the book by Hartmann et al., 2008). Let us note that the “w” shape residual is produced also by the fact that the wings of Voigt functions are Lorentzian, but in the previously investigated cases (Sparavigna, 2023) the wings of the spectrum

are not Lorentzian. Therefore, we can consider further lines from Raman spectroscopy, such as those of the isolated lines of gases, to investigate the behavior of the wings by means of a q-Gaussian power law.

“A wide variety of models of various degrees of complexity have been proposed” to investigate spectral lines and to consider deviations from the Voigt profile: Forthomme and coworkers used the Hartmann-Tran profile. Besides this profile, we can find as quite popular the Rautian and Galatry symmetric profiles, and the asymmetric speed-dependent Voigt profile (Ivanov et al., 2014). The use of the Hartmann-Tran profile (HTP) was recommended in a IUPAC technical report “on line profiles of isolated high-resolution rotational-vibrational transitions perturbed by neutral gas-phase molecules” (Tennyson et al., 2014). Tennyson and coworkers are stressing that the Voigt profile has “well-documented inadequacies” (no references are given, and inadequacies not mentioned at all). Again, we can find told that HT profile “can be computed in a straightforward and rapid manner, and reduces to simpler profiles, including the Voigt profile, under certain simplifying assumptions”. The HT profile is given in Eqs. (5),(6),(7) in [arXiv](#), and it contains seven parameters. According to Table II, the HTP profile can be reduced to Voigt, Rautian, speed-dependent Voigt and speed-dependent Rautian functions. Let us stress, however, that we must calculate the complex Voigt integrals (with error function, see Eq. 6 in the arXiv article) by numerical methods and therefore we have the same problems mentioned above regarding reproducibility. Voigt and complex error functions and related computational methods have been discussed by Schreier, 1992.

The Q(5) line

Being the Tsallis q-Gaussian function characterized by three parameters C, β and q , instead of comparing it with HTP (seven parameters when normalized to unit area), let us consider the Voigt function. We do comparison to understand the behavior of the spectral line wings of gases. Let us start from a Raman line in the Q branch of the carbon monoxide in mixture with Argon, that we can find in an article by Thibault et al., 2002. A plot is available for the Q(5) line and its fitted Voigt function. Here, in the following Figure 3, we show that a q-Gaussian Tsallis function can be fitted onto the same data.

From the Figures 3a,b, we can note that the wings are not Lorentzian. The q parameter is equal to 1.87. This means that the Raman lines of gases are interesting for further research about the power law of line wings.

Thibault and coworkers tell that the “spectral lines were individually fitted to the Voigt profile and the hard collision model profile of Rautian and Sobelman [see references in Thibault et al.]. Since the collisional width determined from both models was within the error bars of the fitted parameter, [Thibault and coworkers] used only the Voigt profile for all measured lines. Figure 1 [in Thibault et al.] shows, as an example, the Q(5) line at 195 K and total pressure of 123.8 mbar for a 3% CO/Ar mixture spectrum. From the observed fitted residuals, it can be seen that the Voigt model fits the observed profile to within the noise”. Being within the noise, the Voigt line is proper for fitting.

The difference between the experimental and fitted q-Gaussian, shown in the lower part of the Figure 5, is of about plus/minus 1%. According to the Figure 1 of Thibault et al., 2002, the Voigt function is giving a difference of about plus/minus 3%. Therefore, our fitted q-Gaussian seems being better than the fitted Voigt function.

In the Figures 3a,b here proposed, data and q-Gaussians are given as functions of integers n (equally spaced points used in fitting), for the x-axis which is representing the Raman shift. A convenient scale is used for the y-axis (intensity axis). The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=270$). Let us repeat again that data have been obtained from the Figure 1 of Thibault et al., 2002.

Fig.3a: The $Q(5)$ Raman line of the carbon monoxide as given in the Figure 1 of the article by Thibault et al., 2002, is here proposed with red points. The peak is at about 2142.75 cm^{-1} . The blue line is its fitted q -Gaussian. The q parameter of this function is equal to 1.87. In the lower part of the figure, the difference between data and q -Gaussian function is given. Note please that the difference is oscillating between plus/minus 1%.

Figure 3b: The same as in the Figure 3a, in semi logarithmic scale.

The fitted q-Gaussian seems being better than the fitted Voigt function, because of its lower misfit, but we have also to remark that both fits are within the noise band, and therefore we cannot assert that one is better than the other.

The Voigt function is usually approximated by a linear combination of a Lorentzian and a Gaussian function. This linear combination is known as the pseudo-Voigt. Here we can try to fit the peak in the Figure 4 with a linear combination of two q-Gaussians. The result is given in the following plot.

Fig.4: The green line is representing the fitted linear combination of two q-Gaussians. The q parameter of the main component is equal to 1.84 . In the lower part of the figure, the difference between data and two-q-Gaussians combination is given. Note please that the difference is oscillating between plus/minus 0.65%.

Is the fit in Figure 4 better than that given in the Fig.3? Of course, the misfit is lower, however both fits are within the noise band, and therefore we cannot assert – without any further measurement - that one is better than the other. In any case, the value of q of the main component changed just of 1.5%.

Discussion

Tennyson and coworkers tell that the “spontaneous emission of radiation is responsible for the natural lifetime broadening or intrinsic line width. This component of the overall line shape is described by a Lorentzian profile which is, however, sufficiently narrow to be safely neglected in favour”, ... of two contributions which are the Doppler effect and the collisional broadening. The “well-known Doppler effect” has a profile (Doppler profile, DP), which is “expressed in terms of the Doppler half-width, Γ_D , by a Gaussian function”. The collisional broadening is producing a Lorentzian profile. “At low pressures the Doppler effect dominates, and as the pressure increases the effects of collisions become increasingly important. As a first approximation to get the resulting line shape, the convolution of an inhomogeneous Doppler profile with a homogeneous Lorentzian profile is commonly used. It defines the so-called VP

[Voigt profile], which contains Doppler and Lorentzian shapes as limiting cases.” (Tennyson et al., 2014). And also: “The standard three-parameter VP, as already mentioned above, is the simplest line shape accounting for the pressure and Doppler effects.” Let us stress once more that the wings of VP are always of the Lorentzian kind.

In Thibault et al., 2002, a detailed discussion is given about the determination of the Lorentzian contribution in the fitted Voigt profile, to evaluate the collisional width. The researchers “fixed the Gaussian width in the Voigt profile to that corresponding to the convolution of the expected Doppler width for every line and temperature, and a Gauss function of 0.0026 cm^{-1} FWHM [full width at half maximum] to account for the apparatus function. Then, the collisional width was obtained as the Lorentz width resulting from the fit”. In our Figure 1, the wings are not Lorentzian, because the fitted q-Gaussian has q-parameter equal to 1.85 . This value of q-parameter tells us that we are closer to a Lorentzian wing than to a Gaussian wing, so the collisional effect seems being quite relevant.

The apparatus

In Thibault et al. we find mentioned the role of the apparatus, given as Gaussian. Actually, when the VP approach is used, many researchers assume that the Gaussian in the convolution is coming from the apparatus, with the result of a pure Lorentzian profile for the photonic emission. However, other effects, such as the Doppler effect considered in Thibault et al., with Gaussian influences participate to the broadening. Moreover, the Dicke effect exists producing a narrowing of Doppler broadening. The Dicke Effect, that is the “collision narrowing”, is the following. In the case that the mean free path of an atom is quite smaller than the wavelength of the radiative transition, a narrowing of the line is produced. The atom is changing its speed and direction several times during photonic emission or absorption. In average on the different Doppler states, we find that the atomic line width is narrower than the Doppler width (Basu, 2007, Demtröder, 1982).

“Of course, the choice of an appropriate line shape function is not a purely theoretical exercise and must be guided by fits to high accuracy measurements, which also need to consider the appropriate instrumental line shape function.” (Tennyson et al., 2014). About the instrumental function and its role in the choice of the line shape, no discussion is given by Tennyson and coworkers.

Time correlation functions

We have previously told that the Fourier transform of Voigt function (time-correlation function) is the product of the Fourier transforms of Lorentzian and Gaussian functions. In Rohart et al., the correlation function of the Voigt model is given as:

$$\Phi = \exp \left[i\omega_0 t - \Gamma t - \left(\frac{kv_{a0}t}{2} \right)^2 \right], \text{ that is: } \Phi = \exp[i\omega_0 t - \Gamma t] \cdot \exp \left[- \left(\frac{kv_{a0}t}{2} \right)^2 \right].$$

ω_0, Γ are the line center frequency and the collisional relaxation rate (given in s^{-1}). The wave number and the most probable value of the absorber speed are $k = \omega_0/c, v_{a0} = \sqrt{2k_B T/m_a}$. T is the temperature, k_B the Boltzmann constant and m_a the molecular mass of the absorber.

Beyond VP, we find in Ngo et al., 2013, mentioned the work by Boone et al., 2007, in relation to the speed-dependent Voigt (SDV) profile. This profile “is the real part of the Fourier transform of the polarization correlation function” as given by Rohart, et al., 2003. The modification of the Voigt function, shown by Rohart et al., maintains the exponential factor related to the Fourier transform of the Lorentzian function, but the Gaussian is substituted by two factors, one of which is containing an irrational function. As proposed in the Eq.9 by Rohart et al., 2003, and Eq.7 in 2008, we have:

$$\Phi = \frac{\exp\{i\omega_0 t - (\Gamma_0 - 3\Gamma_2/2)t\}}{(1+\Gamma_2 t)^{3/2}} \cdot \exp \left\{ \frac{-(kv_{a0}t)^2}{4(1+\Gamma_2 t)} \right\}, \text{ that is}$$

$$\Phi = \exp\{i\omega_0 t - (\Gamma_0 - 3\Gamma_2/2)t\} \cdot \frac{1}{(1+\Gamma_2 t)^{3/2}} \cdot \exp\left\{\frac{-(k v_{a0} t)^2}{4(1+\Gamma_2 t)}\right\} \quad (2)$$

where Γ_0, Γ_2 are the mean relaxation rate over molecular speeds, and the speed dependence of the relaxation rate. Rohart and coworkers are also mentioning the Galatry profile (the HTP has not it as limiting case). So let us show what is the correlation function generating the Galatry profile:

$$\Phi = \exp[i\omega_0 t - \Gamma_0 t] \cdot \exp\left\{\frac{1}{2}(k v_{a0}/B)^2 \cdot \{1 - Bt - \exp(-Bt)\}\right\} \quad (3)$$

where Γ, B are the relaxation rate and the optical diffusion rate. We can find the Galatry profile given also in Dore, 2003.

In Ivanov et al., 2014, the Voigt and the Rautian profiles are formulated in the following manner (see please the parameters y, z defined in the article by Ivanov et al.):

$$f_V(x, y) = R[w(x, y)]; w(x, y) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\exp(-t^2)}{x + iy - t} dt \quad ; \quad f_R(x, y, z) = R\left[\frac{w(x, y+z)}{1 - \sqrt{\pi} \cdot z \cdot w(x, y+z)}\right]$$

For what is regarding the Rautian line shape, we can find it proposed in Rautian and Sobel'man, 1967. "A simultaneous account of radiative decay and the Doppler effect involves no difficulties, since these causes of broadening are statistically independent. As we know, the correlation function in this case equals the product of the correlation functions describing each of the causes of broadening individually". But Rautian and Sobel'man are also stressing that "broadening due to interaction and that due to the Doppler effect are statistically dependent in the general case. Broadening due to interactions involves a phase shift of the atomic oscillator when the atom collides with surrounding particles. Obviously, both the phase of the oscillations and the velocity of translational motion of the atom can be altered in the same collision." For this reason, the Rautian and Sobel'man correlation function is not proposed in the simple forms as in (2) and (3). This is also the case of the correlation giving HTP line shape. Let us add that the Lorentzian profile is not a lower-order line model of HTP, that is, the Lorentzian profile is not given in the Table II by Tennyson et al.

The generalized Kubo case

In Kirillov, 1999, we can find told that the "Gaussian–Markovian, or Kubo case remains the most common and widely used in spectroscopic practice". The correlation is given by (M_2 is the second spectral moment and τ_ω a relaxation time):

$$\Phi = \exp\{-M_2 \tau_\omega^2 [\exp(-t/\tau_\omega) - 1 + t/\tau_\omega]\}, \text{ that is}$$

$$\Phi = \exp\{-M_2 \tau_\omega t\} \cdot \exp\{M_2 \tau_\omega^2 [1 - \exp(-t/\tau_\omega)]\} \quad (4).$$

Here the frequency is referred to the position of the unshifted frequency. Note please once more that correlations (2) and (3), such as (4), have an exponential factor, which is the Fourier transform of a Lorentzian function; that is, we have the line subjected to homogeneous broadening mechanisms. Let us also remember that, considering independent phenomena, they appear as factors in the correlations.

Kirillov, 1999, proposed the time correlation function corresponding to the Egelstaff-Schofield (ES) line shape, in the form that we have previously seen: $g(t) = \exp\{-[(t^2 + \tau_1^2)^{1/2} - \tau_1]/\tau_2\}$, with two relaxation times. In this case, the exponential factor does not appear, as we can find using the Taylor series. Furthermore, Kirillov's research considered also the approach defined as Rothschild-Kubo (Rothschild et al., 1987, Feng and Wilde, 1988).

"Efforts to apply a simple Gauss-Markov theory have proven unsuccessful for aqueous ionic solutions, where strong Coulombic and dipolar forces promote vibrational relaxation, and the hydrogen bonding of the water inhibits anion reorientation. An alternate modeling function, the stretched exponential, has

been proposed to explain inhomogeneously broadened Raman spectra” (Feng & Wilde, 1988). Feng and Wilde consider the “vibrational autocorrelation function $C(t)$, which is obtained by Fourier transforming the isotropic band”. $C(t)$ is given here as:

$$\Phi = \exp\left(i\omega_0 t - \int_0^t (1 - \tau) \chi(\tau) d\tau\right) ; \chi(t) = M_2 \exp\{-(t/T)^\alpha\}$$

M_2 is the second spectral moment.

Rothschild et al., 1987, wrote this time correlation as:

$$\Phi = \exp\left(-M_2 T^2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (t/T)^{2+n\alpha}}{n!(1+n\alpha)(2+n\alpha)}\right) \quad (5)$$

Here we are in the framework of the condensed matter physics. Rothschild and coworkers tell the following. “It has by now been generally accepted that the shapes and widths of band profiles observed by vibrational spectroscopy of condensed-phase systems are, in the vast majority of cases, caused by “inhomogeneous broadening. ... Although spectral profiles of a large variety of liquid-phase systems have since long been satisfactorily explained by this simple Gauss-Markov process ... , more recent and improved spectral data have led to the realization that the experimental vibrational correlation decay in the intermediate to long time domains is occasionally faster (more “Gaussian-like”) than predicted by [the Gauss-Markov approach]”. In Kirillov, 2004, we can find the Rothschild-Perrot-Guillaume (RPG) model as in Eq.(5), discussed with the Burshtein-Fedorenko-Pusep (BFP) model too.

“Differences in TCFs [time correlation functions] lead to very unlike line profiles. ... the Kubo TCF corresponds to vibrational lines whose profiles vary from Gaussian to Lorentzian. The Rothschild-Perrot-Guillaume TCF corresponds to vibrational lines of quite specific, over-Gaussian form. They are less sharp than Gaussian in their central part, and much faster fall to zero in the wings. The Burshtein, Fedorenko and Pusep TCF corresponds to over-Lorentzian line profiles. They are sharper than true Lorentzians in their central part, and broader in the wings” (Kirillov, 2004). We can tell that Kirillov is proposing a generalization of the Kubo correlation function.

Fig.5: Time correlation function (5) for different values of α .

Fig. 6: The same as in the Fig. 5 in semi log scale.

To use (5) in spectroscopy, we need its Fourier transform to determine the corresponding line profile. Being the Fourier transform calculation too heavy for Raman bands deconvolution, Tagliaferro et al., 2020, have proposed a synthetic profile mimicking the lineshape. It is a profile named “GauLor”, which is a piecewise symmetric function with a Lorentzian central part and wings which are Gaussians; actually, it seems being the opposite of the Voigt profile (Gaussian central part and Lorentzian wings). In GauLors, the onset of the wing happens at a frequency threshold, determined by the overall fitting approach. At the threshold, the Lorentzian and Gaussian piece functions and their derivatives are continuous. Supposing the existence of the threshold within the Raman scan range, the GauLor has the onset of the Gaussian wing which can be very close to the center of the line (in the kernel) or quite far from it (in the far line wings). In fact, we have two families of intermediate functions between Lorentzian and Gaussian line shapes, and they are the q-Gaussians and the GauLors.

The Kubo case

Let us consider the Kubo case in the form (super-exponential):

$$\Phi = \exp\{-[\exp(-t) - 1 + t]\},$$

We use here a dimensionless time.

To show the related line shape we need the Fourier transform. To have it, we can pass through the Laplace transform. Here from Wolfram Alpha:

Input interpretation	Result	Alternate form
$\mathcal{L}_t[\exp(-\exp(-\sqrt{t^2}) - \sqrt{t^2} + 1)](s)$	$e(s) - \Gamma(s + 1, 1)$	$e \Gamma(s + 1) - e \Gamma(s + 1, 1)$

Passing from s to $i w$ and evaluating the real part, we have the Fourier transform as:

From the table of values of the function, we find the following line shape in linear and semi log scale.

Fig.8a: Behavior of the Kubo line shape in linear and semi log scale.

In the Lecture Notes by Tokmakoff, 2009, the Kubo time correlation function is given as:

$$F(t) = \exp[-\Delta^2 \tau_c^2 (\exp(-t/\tau_c) + t/\tau_c - 1)]$$

where τ_c is the time scale of dynamics. Parameter $\kappa = \Delta \cdot \tau_c$ is introduced, and three cases are given: fast, $\Delta = 1, \tau_c = 0.2, \kappa = 0.2$, mid, $\Delta = 1, \tau_c = 1, \kappa = 1$, and slow $\Delta = 1, \tau_c = 10, \kappa = 10$. The Absorption lineshapes are given by Tokmakoff as in the following plot (Fig.8b).

Fig.8b.

“We see that for a fixed distribution of frequencies Δ the effect of increasing the time scale of fluctuations through this distribution (decreasing τ_c) is to gradually narrow the observed lineshape from a Gaussian distribution of static frequencies with width (FWHM [Full width at half maximum]) of $2.35 \cdot \Delta$ to a motionally narrowed Lorentzian lineshape with width (FWHM) of $\Delta^2 \tau_c / \pi = \Delta \cdot \kappa / \pi$.” (Tokmakoff, 2009). Here again we are facing the problem to find the “intermediate” function between Lorentzian and Gaussian profiles.

Doppler effect and q-Gaussians

The q-Gaussian Tsallis distribution has been proposed in Silva Jr et al., 1998, where the “Maxwell’s first derivation of the equilibrium distribution function for a dilute gas is generalized in the spirit of the nonextensive q-statistics proposed by Tsallis. As an application, the q-Doppler broadening of spectral lines due to the random thermal motion of the radiating atoms is derived” (Silva Jr et al., 1998). About the broadening of spectral lines, Silva Jr and coworkers tell that the “random motion of particles broadens spectral lines, first, because of collisions between the particles (pressure broadening), and second, due to the thermal Doppler effect of the radiating atoms. As widely known, in the extensive case the first effect is proportional to $pT^{-1/2}$, where p is the pressure, whereas the second scales with $T^{1/2}$ ”. However, the q-Gaussian is a function which can be able of expressing not only the Doppler limiting case, but also the collisional limiting case. Therefore, the q-Gaussian profile needs to be considered in a more general framework. Silva Jr and coworkers discussed the Doppler effect “using the q-Maxwellian velocity distribution”. Plastino and Plastino, March 30, 2023, in their review on the connection between the q-Gaussian and the micro-canonical ensemble, linked the Tsallis functions to the Maxwell’s work (see also Tsallis, 2023). “The unique character of this connection is particularly transparent in the classical non-relativistic regime: within that regime we can say that, to the extent that Nature prefers quadratic kinetic energies, it also prefers q-exponentials. In this regard, it is significative that q-exponentials are clearly discernible in a paper by Maxwell from 1879 [101,102] (see Equation (41) of [102]), which is one of the first papers ever discussing the micro-canonical ensemble, as we call it nowadays. Let us emphasize that Maxwell arrived at the q-exponentials without explicitly optimizing any entropic functional at all, just by assuming equal probabilities in the occupancy of the phase-space corresponding to a given total energy” (Tsallis, 2023). The Ref. [101] and [102] given by Tsallis are Maxwell’s works (Niven, 2013, Maxwell, 1879).

Noise and reproducibility

Thibault and coworkers, 2002, are mentioning the noise. If the fitted line shape is within the noise, we can consider it good for fitting, even if it is not so sophisticated as the HTP one for instance. In the case of the Voigt profile (VP), it is determined by three parameters, the HTP by seven (four of these seven parameters turn being zero in VP). Adkins and Hodges, 2019, in their “Assessment of the precision, bias and numerical correlation of fitted parameters obtained by multi-spectrum fits of the Hartmann-Tran line profile to simulated absorption spectra” tell that “The IUPAC-recommended Hartmann-Tran profile has emerged as a widely utilized spectroscopic model profile for high resolution spectroscopy with the caveat that its use requires *high signal-to-noise* ratio data, adequate constraints, and a wide pressure range”. In their analysis, the researchers considered the behavior of the HTP seven parameters in the limited conditions too (the limiting conditions are those given in the Table II by Tennyson et al., 2014).

About reproducibility in general, we can repeat what told by Adkins and Hodges. “Many laboratories that provide spectroscopic reference data typically use custom software for conducting multi-spectrum HTP fits with known and unknown differences in how the line shape and other parameters are defined.

Differences between models used in the fitting and parameterization for spectroscopic databases can lead to incompatibility in line parameters and down-stream algorithms such that they cannot be used to reproduce fits to experimental data”. Moreover, in the case that we need functions which are numerically calculated, we have also to know the numerical methods used to define the functions which are present in them (that is the used subroutines) and the compiler too. For the same set of data, the knowledge of used parameters, subroutine programs and compilers, can be helpful in the comparison of fitting results. What is fundamental to test reproducibility is the availability of raw and processed data.

Appendix

Some might say that the q-Gaussian function, also known as “Tsallis function”, is a form of the t-Student distribution. Moyano et al., 2006, are indicating that the q-Gaussian “recovers the t-Student distribution with l degrees of freedom if $q = (3 + l)/(l + 1)$. For $l = 1$, hence $q = 2$, we get the Cauchy-Lorentz distribution”. Let us evaluate q as a function of the degrees of freedom (integer values).

Using integers for the degree-of-freedom, the q-parameter has discrete values.

The q-Gaussian is not the t-Student function since we have a different parametrization. If we imagine building a fitting approach of Raman spectra based on t-Student, we have parameter values ranging from 1 to infinity, From the point of view of the numerical approach, the use of a parameter in the range from 1 to 2, or even from 1 to 3, is clearly more convenient.

The t-Student and the q-Gaussian functions are considered to form two different families by Nielsen and Okamura, 2022. “The Cauchy [Lorentzian] distributions belong to two larger families of distributions: Namely, the t-Student distributions (for $v=1$ degrees of freedom) and the q-normal distributions [Naudts] (for $q=2$). ... In information theory, the Cauchy distributions have been used to model and analyze severe non-Gaussian noise with infinite variance ... modeling so-called Cauchy channels” (Nielsen & Okamura, 2022, and references therein). “Cauchy distributions are t-Student distributions with one degree of freedom and thus have heavier tails than Gaussian distributions which make them attractive for analyzing a variety of stochastic phenomena in source/channel coding and quantization” (Nielsen & Okamura mentioning Farvardin & Modestino).

In Wikipedia, we find t-Student = $C \left[1 + \frac{1}{v^2} t^2 \right]^{-(v+1)/2}$, with $C = \frac{\Gamma((v+1)/2)}{\sqrt{v\pi}\Gamma(v/2)}$. It is also told that its characteristic function is ($v > 0$): $\frac{K_{v/2}(\sqrt{v}|t|) \cdot (\sqrt{v}|t|)^{v/2}}{\Gamma(v/2)2^{v/2-1}}$. The characteristic function is the Fourier transform of the probability distribution (calculation in Simon Hurst, 1985).

In Yin and Dong, 2023, we can find the “Bessel function expression of characteristic function”. The researchers are proposing a “unified method to derive the classical characteristic functions of all elliptical and related distributions in terms of Bessel functions”. They are presenting “the simple closed form of characteristic functions for commonly used distributions such as multivariate t , Pearson Type II, Pearson Type VII, Kotz type and Bessel distributions”, so we can enlarge the basin of functions which can be investigated by means of WolframAlpha. In fact, in Yin and Dong [arXiv](#), we can find the modified Bessel function of the second kind, with order ν , defined by the following WolframAlpha integral:

$$\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \int_0^{\infty} (1+w^2)^{-(\nu+1/2)} \cos(tw) dw = \frac{2^{1/2-\nu} |t|^\nu K_\nu(t \operatorname{sgn}(t))}{\Gamma(\nu + \frac{1}{2})}$$

This is the Fourier transform that we can obtain by means of the WolframAlpha software of function $(1+w^2)^{-(\nu+1/2)}$.

The expression of Pearson Type VII, is given in <https://www.originlab.com/doc/Origin-Help/PearsonVII-FitFunc> for instance, where it is told that the “peak function is a Lorentz function raised to a power”. In this case too we can use WolframAlpha to obtain its Fourier transform and therefore its time correlation function.

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